

An Expression A Day

AEAD PDF Book

No. 201-300 / 100 entries

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It doesn't matter

どうでもいい

Doudemoii

It doesn't matter

Variants

- どうでもいい
it doesn't matter
- そんなことどうでもいい
who cares
- ~なんてどうでもいい
I don't care about that

Adjusted Expression

ぞう たいじゅう なんきろゾウの体重が何キロであるかは、じゅうよう重要ではない。

It is not important how many kilograms an elephant weighs.

Example

ぞう たいじゅう なんきろゾウの体重が何キロかなんてどうでもいい。

Who cares how much an elephant weighs?

Notes

"Doudemo ii" is used to express that something doesn't matter or that you don't care about it. The word "doudemo" is an adverb that means "anyway" or "in any case." The word "ii" is an adjective that means "good."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing that something is not important

expressing lack of interest

dismissing a topic

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

evaluative expression

indifference

topic management

Where have you been?

どこ^い行ってた？

Doko itteta?

Where have you been?

Variants

- どこ行ってた？
Where have you been?
- どこに行ってたの？
Where did you go?
- 今までどこ行ってた？
Where were you?

Adjusted Expression

いま^いまでどこに行っていたのですか。

Where have you been until now?

Example

A 「どこ行ってた？」 B 「ちょっと、そこまで」 A 「探^{さが}してたよ」

A: Where have you been? B: Just over there. A: I was looking for you.

Notes

"Doko itteta?" is used to ask where someone has been or to tell them that you were looking for them. The word "doko" is a noun that means

"where." The word "itta" is the past tense of the verb "iku," which means "to go."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

asking where someone has been

implying that one was looking for the person

immediate reaction to someone's return

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

question expression

absence

checking on someone

Room to spare

よゆう
余裕

Yoyuu

Room to spare

Variants

- 余裕
room to spare
- 余裕がある
have leeway
- 時間に余裕がある
have enough time

Adjusted Expression

じかん きもち よゆう 時間や気持ちに余裕があると、しごと らく すす 仕事を楽に進められる。

When you have enough time and mental room, you can proceed with your work more easily.

Example

よゆう 余裕があると、しごと らく すす 仕事も楽に進められる。

When you have room to spare, you can work more easily.

Notes

"Yoyuu ga aru" is used to express that you have time or space to do something. The word "yoyuu" is a noun that means "leeway" or "margin." The word "aru" is a verb that means "to exist."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing temporal or spatial leeway

expressing mental room

explaining ease of work

Tags EN

immediate grammar

noun

colloquial

leeway

time expression

work

It's this late already

もうこんな^{じかん}時間

Mou konna jikan

It's this late already

Variants

- もうこんな時間
It's this late already
- もうこんな時間だ
It's already this time
- もうこんな時間になっていた
Time has passed so quickly

Adjusted Expression

^{じかん}時間が^{おも}思ったより^{おそ}遅くなっている。

It is later than I expected.

Example

もうこんな^{じかん}時間、^{はや}早く^{かえ}帰らないと。

It's already this late. I need to get home soon.

Notes

"Mou konna jikan" is used to express that it is already a certain time. It is used when you are a little surprised and in a hurry. The word "mou" is an adverb that means "already." The word "konna" is a demonstrative

pronoun that means "this kind of." The word "jikan" is a noun that means "time."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

surprise at the passage of time

sharing the need to hurry

prompting action

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

time expression

surprise

hurry

Have to do something

なんとかしなきゃ

Nantoka shinakya

Have to do something

Variants

- なんとかしなきゃ
have to do something
- なんとかしないと
I have to do something about it
- なんとかしなくちゃ
something has to be done

Adjusted Expression

(この)問題^{たい}に対して、何かの対応^{なに たいおう}をしなければならぬ。

I must take some action regarding this problem.

Example

この問題^{もんだい}、なんとかしなきゃ。

I have to do something about this problem.

Notes

"Nantoka shinakya" is used to express that you have to do something about a situation or problem. The word "nantoka" is an adverb that means "somehow" or "in some way." The word "shinakya" is a contraction of the phrase "shinakereba naranai," which means "must do."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing the need to deal with a problem

sharing urgency

showing determination to act

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

problem handling

obligation expression

urgency

Step-by-step guidance

てと あしと
手取り足取り

Tetori ashitori

Step-by-step guidance

Variants

- 手取り足取り
step-by-step guidance
- 手取り足取り教える
teach carefully step by step
- 手取り足取り指導する
guide someone carefully

Adjusted Expression

かれ ひと ひと ていねい おし
彼は、一つ一つ丁寧に教えてくれた。

He taught me each step carefully.

Example

かれ てと あしと おし
彼は手取り足取り教えてくれた。

He provided step-by-step guidance.

Notes

"Tetori ashitori" is used to express that you are guided step by step or hand in hand. In reality, your hands or feet are not touched, so this expression means that you are kindly and carefully taught.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing careful guidance

expressing teaching in detail

evaluating a kind way of teaching

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

guidance

carefulness

kindness

Part-time job

あ る ば い と
アルバイト

Arubaito

Part-time job

Variants

- アルバイト
part-time job
- バイト
part-time work
- アルバイトをする
work part-time

Adjusted Expression

かれ しゅう かい か ふ え 仕事
彼は、週に3回、カフェで(パートタイム)の仕事をしています。

He works at a cafe three times a week on a part-time basis.

Example

かれ しゅう かい か ふ え ある ば い と
彼は週に3回、カフェでアルバイトをしています。

He works part-time at a cafe three times a week.

Notes

"Arubaito" is a loanword from the German word "Arbeit," which means "work." The word "arubaito" is a noun that means "part-time job."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing a type of work

describing daily life

mentioning employment style

Tags EN

immediate grammar

noun

loanword

work

everyday vocabulary

Forgot

わす
忘れてしまった

Wasurete shimatta

Forgot

Variants

- 忘れてしまった
forgot
- すっかり忘れてしまった
completely forgot
- 誕生日を忘れてしまった
forgot the birthday

Adjusted Expression

きのう つま たんじょうび しつねん
昨日、妻の誕生日を失念した。

I failed to remember my wife's birthday yesterday.

Example

きのう つま たんじょうび わす
昨日、妻の誕生日を忘れてしまった。

I forgot my wife's birthday yesterday.

Notes

"Wasurete shimatta" is used to express that you forgot something. The word "wasurete" is the te-form of the verb "wasureru," which means "to forget." The word "shimatta" is a contraction of the phrase

"shimaimashita," which means "to have done something." When you use "te shimatta," it implies that you did something unintentionally or regretfully.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

reporting a mistake

expressing regret

expressing that one forgot unintentionally

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

mistake expression

regret

unintentional action

What am I doing?

なに
何やってんだ？

Nani yattenda?

What am I doing?

Variants

- 何やってんだ？
What am I doing?
- 何やってるんだ？
What are you doing?
- 何してるんだ？
What is going on?

Adjusted Expression

じぶん なに 何をしているのか、わ 分からなくなっている。

I am no longer sure what I am doing.

Example

なに
何やってんだ？

What am I doing?

Notes

"Nani yattenda?" is used to express that you are surprised or confused about your own actions. The word "nani" is a pronoun that means "what." The word "yattenda" is a contraction of the phrase "yatte iru n

da," which means "doing." It is a so-called "talking to oneself" expression, but it is often used.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

surprise at one's own action

expressing confusion

reaction as self-talk

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

self-talk

surprise

confusion

What should I do?

どうしよう？

Dou shiyou?

What should I do?

Variants

- どうしよう？
What should I do?
- どうしましょう？
What shall I do?
- どうすればいい？
What should we do?

Adjusted Expression

こんなん じょうきょう なに
困難な状況で、何をすればよいか分からない。

I do not know what I should do in this difficult situation.

Example

あ、こま困った。どうしよう？

Oh no, what should I do?

Notes

"Dou shiyou/shimashou?" is a soliloquy used when you are in a difficult situation and don't know what to do. The word "dou" is an interrogative pronoun that means "how." The word "shimashou" is a polite expression

of the verb "suru," which means "to do." This is used when you are talking to yourself.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

self-talk in a difficult situation

looking for a way to deal with something

expressing anxiety or hesitation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

self-talk

perplexity

consultative expression

The strongest

さいきょう
最強

Saikyou

The strongest

Variants

- 最強
the strongest
- 最強のチーム
the strongest team
- 最強だ
be the strongest

Adjusted Expression

かれ もっと つよ ち む しょぞく
彼は、最も強いチームに所属している。

He belongs to the strongest team.

Example

A 「このメンバーなら絶対勝ね」 B 「そうだね、最強だね」

A: With these members, we will definitely win. B: That's right, we are the strongest.

Notes

"Saikyou" is used to express that something is the strongest or most powerful. The word "saikyou" is a noun that means "the strongest."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing the highest degree of strength

evaluating ability or power

expressing strong praise

Tags EN

immediate grammar

noun

evaluative expression

strength

superlative

At this point

いまさら
今更

Imasara

At this point

Variants

- 今更
at this point
- 今更遅い
it's too late now
- 今更謝っても遅い
it's too late to apologize now

Adjusted Expression

いま あやま 謝っても、もう おそ 遅い。

Even if you apologize now, it is already too late.

Example

いまさら あやま 今更、謝っても おそ 遅いよ。

It's too late to apologize now.

Notes

"Imasara" is used to express that it is too late to do something. The word "imasara" is an adverb that means "now" or "at this point."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing that it is too late

pointing out that the timing has been missed

negative evaluation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

adverb

colloquial

time expression

too late

negative evaluation

That's not true

それはない

Sore wa nai

That's not true

Variants

- それはない
that's not true
- それはないよ
that's impossible
- それはありえない
that can't be right

Adjusted Expression

かれ かれ うそ うそ がついていて おも いるということは、かんが かんが にくい。

It is unlikely that he is lying.

Example

A 「かれ かれ うそ うそ、ついてると おも 思う？」 B 「それはない」

A: Do you think he's lying? B: That's not true.

Notes

"Sore wa nai" is used to express that something is not true or impossible. The word "sore" is a pronoun that means "that." The word "wa" is a particle that is used to indicate the topic of a sentence. The word "nai" is an i-adjective that means "not exist" or "not be."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing denial

denying possibility

reacting to someone's judgment

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

denial

possibility

Once a week

しゅういち
週 1

Shuuichi

Once a week

Variants

- 週1
once a week
- 週1で
weekly
- 週1でジムに行く
go to the gym once a week

Adjusted Expression

しゅう かい じむ い
週に1回、ジムに行っている。

I go to the gym once a week.

Example

しゅういち じむ い
週 1で、ジムに行っている。

I go to the gym once a week.

Notes

"Shuuichi" is used to express that something happens once a week. The word "shuu" is a noun that means "week." The word "ichi" is a number that means "one." The word "de" is a particle that is used to indicate the

frequency of an action. By the same token, "shuuni" means "twice a week," "shuusan" means "three times a week," and so on.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing frequency

describing a habit

sharing a life rhythm

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

frequency expression

habit

numerical expression

Tuesday and Thursday

かもく
火木

Kamoku

Tuesday and Thursday

Variants

- 火木
Tuesday and Thursday
- 火木で
on Tuesdays and Thursdays
- 火木に
every Tuesday and Thursday

Adjusted Expression

かようび もくようび じゅうどう けいこ い
火曜日と木曜日に、柔道の稽古に行っている。

I go to judo practice on Tuesdays and Thursdays.

Example

かもく じゅうどう けいこ い
火木で柔道の稽古に行っている。

I go to judo practice on Tuesdays and Thursdays.

Notes

"Kamoku" means "kayoubi" (Tuesday) and "mokuyoubi" (Thursday). In the same way, "donichi" means "doyoubi" (Saturday) and "nichiyoubi" (Sunday).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing a combination of weekdays

explaining schedule frequency

describing a habit

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

weekday expression

frequency expression

schedule

Time-limited offer

た い む さ ー び す
タイムサービス

Taimu saabisu

Time-limited offer

Variants

- タイムサービス
time-limited offer
- タイムセール
limited-time sale
- 今だけ半額
half price for now

Adjusted Expression

この商品は、しょうひん今いまだけ半額はんがくで販売はんばいされています。

This product is being sold at half price for a limited time.

Example

この商品は、しょうひん今いま、た い む さ ー び すタイムサービスで半額はんがくです。

This product is half price with a time-limited offer.

Notes

"Taimu saabisu" is used to express that a product or service is available at a discounted price for a limited time. The word "taimu" is a noun that

means "time." The word "saabisu" is a noun that means "service." "Taimu seeru" is also used.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing a limited-time discount

expressing sales promotion

shopping situation expression

Tags EN

immediate grammar

noun

loanword

shopping

discount

limited time

Having said that

とは^い言っても

To wa itte mo

Having said that

Variants

- とは言っても
having said that
- そうは言っても
that said
- 忙しいとは言っても
even so

Adjusted Expression

かれ いそが てつだ
彼は忙しいが、手伝ってくれる。

He is busy, but he will help you.

Example

かれ いそが い てつだ
彼は忙しい。とは言っても、手伝ってくれるよ。

He's busy. Having said that, he will help you.

Notes

"To wa itte mo" is used to express a contrast or contradiction. The word "to" is a particle that is used to indicate a quotation. The word "wa" is a particle that is used to indicate the topic of a sentence. The word "itte" is

the te-form of the verb "iu," which means "to say." The word "mo" is a particle that is used to indicate that the speaker is adding information.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

qualifying a previous statement

introducing contrast

softening a condition

Tags EN

immediate grammar

connective expression

discourse marker

contrast

qualification

Sometimes

たまに

Tamani

Sometimes

Variants

- たまに
sometimes
- たまには
once in a while
- たまに食べたくなる
sometimes feel like eating

Adjusted Expression

ふだん 普段は いんすたんとらーめん インスタントラーメンを た 食べないようにしているが、 ときどきた 時々食べたくなる
ことがある。

I usually try not to eat instant noodles, but sometimes I feel like eating them.

Example

いんすたんとらーめん インスタントラーメンは た なるべく食べないようにしているが、 た たまに食べたく
なることがある。

I try not to eat instant noodles as much as possible, but sometimes I feel like eating them.

Notes

"Tamani" means sometimes or occasionally. "Narutake" means as much as possible. "Tabetakunaru" means to feel like eating. "Koto ga aru" is used to express that something happens occasionally.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing frequency

expressing an occasional desire

temporary deviation from a habit

Tags EN

immediate grammar

adverb

colloquial

frequency expression

desire expression

Well, you know

まあね

Maane

Well, you know

Variants

- まあね
well, you know
- まあ、そうだね
well, yeah
- まあねえ
I guess so

Adjusted Expression

つよ強くは同意どういしないが、ある程度ていどは理解りかいしている。

I do not strongly agree, but I understand it to some extent.

Example

A 「こんなことしたくないよね」 B 「まあね」

A: I don't want to do this. B: Well, you know.

Notes

"Maane" is an expression of passive agreement or understanding. While it conveys a sense of agreement, it is often used when one does not want to fully commit to agreeing or disagreeing. This makes it convenient in situations where one wishes to remain non-committal. When you hear

this expression, it is best not to expect too much enthusiasm or certainty from the speaker.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

passive agreement

ambiguous response

non-committal response

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

ambiguous response

passive agreement

Oh well

ま、いっか

Ma, ikka

Oh well

Variants

- ま、いっか
oh well
- まあ、いいか
never mind
- もういいか
that's okay

Adjusted Expression

すこ ざんねん しかた
少し残念だが、仕方がない。

It is a little disappointing, but it cannot be helped.

Example

A 「今日のお弁当は、すべて売り切れました」 B 「ま、いっか」

A: Today's bento boxes are all sold out. B: Oh well, never mind.

Notes

"Ma, ikka" is used to express that you don't care about something or that you are not bothered by something. The word "ma" is an interjection that is used to express hesitation or uncertainty. The word "ikka" is a contraction of the phrase "ii ka," which means "it's okay."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing resignation

letting something pass

shifting one's mood

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

resignation

letting it pass

Not exactly that

そんなわけ訳でもなくて

Sonna wake demo nakute

Not exactly that

Variants

- そんな訳でもなくて
not exactly that
- そういう訳でもなくて
not really for that reason
- 別にそんな訳でもなくて
it's not quite like that

Adjusted Expression

あいて相手のかんが考えている理由ちがとは、少し違う。

The reason is a little different from what the other person thinks.

Example

A 「昨日、遅くまで起きていたの？」 B 「そんなわけ訳でもなくて、映画えいがを見ていたら時間じかんが経たってしまった」

A: Were you up late last night? B: Not exactly that. I was watching a movie, and time just passed before I knew it.

Notes

"Sonna wake demo nakute" is used to express that the reason for something is not what the other person thinks. The word "sonna" is a demonstrative pronoun that means "that kind of." The word "wake" is a noun that means "reason." The word "demo" is a conjunction that means "but" or "however." The word "nakute" is the 'te-form' of the verb "nai," which means "to not be." In some cases, the reason given by the other person isn't exactly wrong, but it also suggests that it wasn't intended to be that way.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

softly denying someone's assumption

correcting the reason

expressing that it was not intentional

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

reason explanation

soft denial

correction

It can't be helped

しょうがないね

Shou ga nai ne

It can't be helped

Variants

- しょうがないね
it can't be helped
- しょうがない
there's nothing we can do
- 仕方ないね
that's too bad, but okay

Adjusted Expression

じょうきょう か 状 況を変えることはできないので、こんかい う い 今回は受け入れる。

Since the situation cannot be changed, I will accept it this time.

Example

きゅう よてい はい 急に予定が入った？しょうがないね、またこんど今度にしよう。

Did something suddenly come up? It can't be helped. Let's do it another time.

Notes

"Shou ga nai ne" expresses acceptance of a situation that can't be changed. The word "shou" comes from "shiyou," meaning "way." This

phrase is used not only when something is unavoidable, but also to convey acceptance.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

accepting the situation

showing consideration for the other person

reacting to a schedule change

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

acceptance

consideration

schedule change

How should I put it

なんていうか

Nante iu ka

How should I put it

Variants

- なんていうか
how should I put it
- なんというか
how can I say this
- なんて言えばいいか
I don't quite know how to put it

Adjusted Expression

てきせつ ことば さが い かれ さいきん いそが
適切な言葉を探しながら言うと、彼は最近忙しいのかもしれない。

To put it carefully, he may have been busy lately.

Example

A 「かれ 彼、さいきん 最近、へん 変だよ」 B 「いそが なんていうか、忙しいのかな」

A: He's been acting strange lately. B: How should I put it, maybe he's busy.

Notes

"Nanteiuka" is used to express that you are trying to find the right words to describe something. The word "nante" is an interrogative pronoun that means "what kind of." The word "iu" is a verb that means "to say."

The word "ka" is a particle that is used to indicate a question. However, it is used in various contexts, so it can be considered almost meaningless.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

searching for the right words

hesitation before speaking

presenting a vague impression

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

discourse marker

hesitation

vague expression

That's true!

たし
確かに

Tashika ni

That's true!

Variants

- 確かに
that's true
- 確かにね
you're right
- 確かにそうだね
now that you mention it

Adjusted Expression

あいて してき ただ
相手の指摘は正しい。

The other person's point is correct.

Example

A 「彼、^{かれ}最近、^{さいきん}変だよね」 B 「確かに」

A: He's been acting strange lately. B: You're right.

Notes

"Tashikani" means "certainly" or "surely." However, it is more commonly used to express agreement or realization, like "You're right" or "I see."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing agreement

reacting to someone's point

sharing realization

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

agreement

realization

For now

と
取りあえず

Toriaezu

For now

Variants

- とりあえず
for now
- とりあえず今日はここまで
let's stop here for today
- とりあえずやってみる
try it for now

Adjusted Expression

どうめん 当面は、きょう 今日はここまでにする。

For the time being, we will stop here today.

Example

とりあえず、きょう 今日はここまで。

For now, let's stop here today.

Notes

"Toriaezu" is used to express that you are doing something temporarily or for the time being. The word "toriaezu" is an adverb that means "for now" or "for the time being."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing a provisional decision

marking a temporary stopping point

presenting an immediate action

Tags EN

immediate grammar

adverb

colloquial

provisionality

stopping point

starting action

Looks good

よ
良さそう

Yosasou

Looks good

Variants

- 良さそう
looks good
- ちょうど良さそう
looks just right
- これ良さそう
this looks good

Adjusted Expression

(この)サイズは、ちょうど良いように見える。

This size appears to be just right.

Example

このサイズ、ちょうど良さそう！

This size looks just right!

Notes

"Yosasou" is used to express that something looks good or seems to be good. The word "yosasou" is an adjective that means "looks good" or

"seems good." "Yoi" is an alternative to "ii" and is used to avoid saying "iisou" which is difficult to say.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

- judging from appearance
- expressing that something seems just right
- giving a light positive evaluation

Tags EN

- immediate grammar
- colloquial
- evaluative expression
- conjecture
- appearance-based judgment

Premonition

よかん
予感

Yokan

Premonition

Variants

- 予感
premonition
- いい予感
good premonition
- 悪い予感
bad premonition

Adjusted Expression

きょう なに い お かん
今日は、何か良いことが起こりそうだと感じる。

I feel that something good may happen today.

Example

きょう なに い よかん
今日は何か良いことがありそうな予感がする。

I have a premonition that something good will happen today.

Notes

"Yokan" is used to express that you have a feeling or intuition about something that will happen in the future. The word "yokan" is a noun

that means "premonition" or "hunch." "ii yokan" is used to express a good premonition, and "warui yokan" is used to express a bad premonition.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing intuition about the future

expressing a feeling that something good may happen

sharing a weakly grounded expectation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

noun

sensory expression

intuition

future

Pathetic

なさ
情けない

Nasakenai

Pathetic

Variants

- 情けない
pathetic
- 情けないね
that's pathetic
- 自分が情けない
I feel pathetic

Adjusted Expression

じぶん じゅうぶん なに ざんねん おも
自分が十分に何もできないことを、残念に思う。

I feel disappointed that I am unable to do enough.

Example

こんなに何もできないなんて、情けない。

It's pathetic that I can't do anything.

Notes

"Nasakenai" is used to express that something or someone is pitiful or pathetic. It can also be used when one feels disappointed in oneself for being inadequate.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

negative evaluation of oneself

expressing a sense of inadequacy

expressing disappointment

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

emotional expression

self-evaluation

disappointment

Quite

かなり

Kanari

Quite

Variants

- かなり
quite
- かなり難しい
quite difficult
- かなり大きい
fairly large

Adjusted Expression

この実験じっけんを成功せいこうさせるのは、相当そうとう難むづかしい。

It is considerably difficult to make this experiment successful.

Example

この実験じっけんを成功せいこうさせるのは、かなり難むづかしい。

It's quite difficult to make this experiment successful.

Notes

"Kanari" is used to express that something is quite or fairly. The word "kanari" is an adverb that means "quite" or "fairly." It is used to express that something is more than expected or more than usual.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

emphasizing degree

expressing something more than expected

strengthening an evaluation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

adverb

colloquial

degree expression

emphasis

It's better to

ほう
-た方がいい

-ta hou ga ii

It's better to

Variants

- -た方がいい
it's better to
- 早く寝た方がいい
you should
- ～した方がいい
it would be better to

Adjusted Expression

しけん ぜんじつ はや ね のぞ
試験の前日は、早く寝ることが望ましい。

It is advisable to go to bed early on the day before the exam.

Example

しけん ぜんじつ べんきょう てん よ はや ね
試験の前日は、勉強しても点が良くなるわけではないので、早く寝たほうが
いい。

You should go to bed early because studying the day before the exam
doesn't necessarily improve your score.

Notes

"-ta hou ga ii" is used to express that it is better to do something. The word "hou" is a noun that means "way" or "direction." The word "ii" is an adjective that means "good."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

giving advice

presenting a better choice

sharing a judgment with someone

Tags EN

immediate grammar

sentence pattern expression

colloquial

advice

judgment

Just now

たった今^{いま}

Tatta ima

Just now

Variants

- たった今
just now
- たった今送った
just sent it
- たった今終わった
just finished

Adjusted Expression

いましがた、メールを送信したので、かくにん確認してください。

I sent the email a moment ago, so please check it.

Example

たった今、メールを送ったのでかくにん確認してください。

I just sent an email, so please check it.

Notes

"Tattaima" is used to express that something happened just now. The word "tatta" is an adverb that means "just" or "only." The word "ima" is a noun that means "now."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing something that happened just before

reporting immediate completion

asking someone to check

Tags EN

immediate grammar

adverbial expression

colloquial

time expression

just now

completion report

How come?

なん
何で

Nande

How come?

Variants

- 何で
how come?
- なんで
why?
- なんで遅れるの？
why is it late?

Adjusted Expression

きょう でんしゃ おく りゆう なん
今日、電車が遅れる理由は何ですか。

What is the reason the train is late today?

Example

きょう でんしゃ なん おく
今日、電車、何で遅れるの？

How come the train is late today?

Notes

"Nannde" is used to express that you are surprised or curious about something. The word "nannde" is an interrogative pronoun that means

"how come?" or "why?" Sometimes it is used to criticize something bad.
In Osaka dialect, it would be "nande ya nen."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

asking for a reason

expressing surprise or curiosity

expressing light criticism

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

question expression

reason

surprise

criticism

No way

まさか

Masaka

No way

Variants

- まさか
no way
- まさかあ
you can't be serious
- まさかそんな
that can't be true

Adjusted Expression

あした ゆき ふ 明日、雪が降るとはしん信じられない。

I cannot believe that it will snow tomorrow.

Example

A 「あす明日、ゆき雪、ふ降るらしいよ」 B 「まさかあ」

A: It seems like it's going to snow tomorrow. B: No way.

Notes

"Masaka" is used to express that you are surprised or don't believe something. The word "masaka" is an adverb that means "no way" or "impossible."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing surprise

expressing disbelief

immediate reaction to someone's statement

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

surprise

disbelief

That's true

それはそうだ

Sore wa sou da

That's true

Variants

- それはそうだ
that's true
- それはそうだね
that's certainly true
- それは確かにそうだ
you're right about that

Adjusted Expression

あいて い 相手の言ったことは、たし ただ 確かに正しい。

What the other person said is certainly correct.

Example

A 「やっぱり健康が一番大事だと思うよ」 B 「それはそうだ。健康がなければ何も始まらないよね」

A: I think health is the most important thing after all. B: That's true.

Without health, nothing can start.

Notes

"Sore wa sou da" is used to express that you totally agree with what the other person said. The word "sore" is a pronoun that means "that." The

word "wa" is a particle that is used to indicate the topic of a sentence. The word "souda" is a contraction of the phrase "sou da," which means "that's true." In a more casual way, you can say "sorya sou da."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing strong agreement

accepting what the other person said

confirming a premise

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

agreement

confirmation

That's not fair

そりゃないよ

Sorya nai yo

That's not fair

Variants

- そりゃないよ
that's not fair
- それはないよ
come on, that's not right
- それはひどいよ
that's too much

Adjusted Expression

やくそく 約束していたのに、きょうこ 今日来られないのはざんねん 残念だ。

It is disappointing that you cannot come today even though you had promised.

Example

A 「ごめん、やくそく 約束してたけどきょうい 今日行けなくなった」 B 「えー、そりゃないよ！
たの 楽しみにしてたのに」

A: Sorry, I can't go today even though I promised. B: Come on, that's not fair! I was looking forward to it.

Notes

"Sorya nai yo" is used to express that you are disappointed or surprised by something. The word "sorya" is a contraction of the phrase "sore wa," which means "that is." The word "nai yo" means "there is no" or "that's not acceptable" in this expression.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing disappointment

showing dissatisfaction with someone's action

reacting to disappointed expectations

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

disappointment

dissatisfaction

Do you have to go that far?

そこまで言う？

Soko made iu?

Do you have to go that far?

Variants

- そこまで言う？
do you have to go that far?
- そこまで言わなくても
you don't have to say that much
- そこまで言う必要ある？
isn't that going too far?

Adjusted Expression

あいてい かた すこ きび
相手の言い方は、少し厳しすぎる。

The other person's way of saying it is a little too harsh.

Example

A 「その服、趣味悪いよ」 B 「そこまで言う？」

A: That outfit is in bad taste. B: Do you have to go that far?

Notes

"Soko made iu?" is used to express feelings of surprise or being hurt by something. It is a concise yet effective phrase for conveying mild astonishment or a light protest. The particle made indicates a range or

limit. Used in this way, it suggests that the other person's words were unexpected or felt a bit harsh, effectively conveying the sense of "going too far."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

reacting to something going too far

light protest

expressing hurt feelings

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

protest

going too far

In that sense, ...

そういう意味で、...

Sou iu imi de, ...

In that sense, ...

Variants

- そういう意味で
in that sense
- そういう意味では
in that respect
- そういう意味で、むしろ
seen that way

Adjusted Expression

別の観点から見ると、その会議には一定の成果があった。

From another point of view, the meeting had some value.

Example

わずかですが、とても貴重な意見が得られました。そういう意味で、むしろ会議は成功だったと思います。

We received only a few comments, but they were very valuable. In that sense, I believe the meeting was actually a success.

Notes

"Sou iu imi de" is used to highlight positive aspects of a situation that is less than ideal. It connects a statement of value to an otherwise unsatisfactory context. This phrase is often used to find something good, however small, in a project that may have otherwise been a failure, allowing one to present the results in a more positive light. It is also used to encourage someone who is feeling down after a failed project, by pointing out even the smallest positive outcome to lift their spirits.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

presenting a positive aspect

reevaluating failure or insufficiency

comforting or encouraging someone

Tags EN

immediate grammar

connective expression

discourse marker

reevaluation

positive interpretation

comforting

Not that much...

それほどでも...

Sore hodo demo...

Not that much...

Variants

- それほどでも
not that much
- いいえ、それほどでも
not really
- いや、それほどでもないです
no, not that much

Adjusted Expression

じぶん 自分は、すぐそこまで優れているとは思っていない。おも

I do not think I am that good.

Example

A 「君は記憶力がいいねえ」 B 「いいえ、それほどでも」

A: You have a good memory. B: Not that much.

Notes

The phrase "sore hodo demo" is used to express that something is not as much as expected or mentioned. It is also used to modestly respond when you are praised. In Japanese, you cannot say "Yes, that's right" when you are praised, so you use a humble expression. However, the

inner thoughts of student B who is praised by teacher A are certainly happy. If you think it's a lie, try answering "Yes, that's right" once. You may become popular, but I think it's better not to say that.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing modesty

responding to praise

softening an evaluation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

modesty

response to praise

I'm tired of it

あ
飽きた

Akita

I'm tired of it

Variants

- 飽きた
I'm tired of it
- 食べ飽きた
I'm tired of eating it
- 聞き飽きた
I'm tired of hearing it

Adjusted Expression

おな 同じことを繰り返すことに、きょうみ うしな 興味を失っている。

I have lost interest in repeating the same thing.

Example

A 「毎日、同じこと、ばっかしていると、飽きたよね」 B 「うん、新しいこと、始めたい」

A: Doing the same thing every day gets boring. B: Yeah, I want to start something new.

Notes

"Akita" expresses that you are tired of something or bored with it. This expression is often used in the form of a compound verb such as "tabeakita" (get tired of eating) or "miakita" (get tired of seeing).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing being tired of something

expressing weariness from repetition

wanting something new

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

emotional expression

boredom

compound verb

Big brother

にい
お兄さん

Oniisan

Big brother

Variants

- お兄さん
big brother
- 兄さん
older brother
- お兄ちゃん
young man

Adjusted Expression

としうえ だんせい たい した ふく こしょう
年上の男性に対する親しみを含む呼称である。

It is a familiar term of address for an older male.

Example

にい てつだ
お兄さん、手伝ってくれる？

Big brother, can you help me?

Notes

"Oniisan" means "big brother" in Japanese. It is used to refer to an older brother or a young man who is older than the speaker even if he is not a

brother. It is better not to use it for someone you don't know, because you may be regarded as vulgar. Of course, "oneesan" is the same.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

addressing an older brother

referring to an older young man

addressing someone with familiarity

Tags EN

immediate grammar

noun

address term

family vocabulary

interpersonal relations

expression requiring caution

True feelings

ねえ、^{ほんしん}本心は？

Nee, honshin wa?

What are your true feelings?

Variants

- 本心は？
what are your true feelings?
- ねえ、本心は？
what do you really think?
- 本当はどう思ってるの？
what is your real intention?

Adjusted Expression

^{ほんとう}本当に^{おも}どう思っているのかを^{かくにん}確認しています。

I am checking what you really think.

Example

A 「^{きみ}君が^{ひつよう}必要です」 B 「ねえ、^{ほんしん}本心は？」

A: I need you. B: What are your true feelings? You don't really think so, do you?

Notes

"Honshin wa?" is used to ask what the other person really thinks. The word "honshin" is a noun that means "true feelings" or "real intention."

Even if someone says "I love you" or "I need you," it may not always be sincere. This question, "Honshin wa?" asks for their genuine feelings, often suggesting doubt or skepticism.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

asking for someone's true feelings

showing doubt about what was said

checking someone's real intention

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

question expression

true feelings

doubt

checking real intention

Perfect

かんぺき
完璧

Kanpeki

Perfect

Variants

- 完璧
perfect
- 完璧だった
was perfect
- 完璧なプレゼン
a perfect presentation

Adjusted Expression

きょう ぶれ ぜん てー し ょん けってん み あ
今日のプレゼンテーションは、欠点が見当たありませんでしたよ。

Today's presentation was flawless, without any noticeable flaws.

Example

A 「今日のプレゼン、完璧だったね」 B 「ありがとう」

A: Today's presentation was perfect. B: Thank you.

Notes

"Kanpeki" is used to express that something is perfect or flawless. The word "kanpeki" is an adjective that means "perfect" or "flawless." It is used to express that something is without any mistakes or flaws. If you

look closely at the kanji for "kanpeki," you will see that the character "完" means "complete" and "璧" means "without flaws." When you observe the character "璧" closely, you will see that there is a "玉" at the bottom. This is the "玉" used in the word "gyokuseki" (jewel), which has a beautiful surface without any flaws. Be careful not to confuse the character "璧" with the character "壁" (kabe), which means "wall." The character "壁" has "土" at the bottom, so be careful not to make a mistake. You won't be perfect.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing high evaluation

expressing flawlessness

expressing praise

Tags EN

immediate grammar

na-adjective

evaluative expression

praise

perfection

Method

ほうほう
方法

Houhou

Method

Variants

- 方法
method
- この方法
this method
- 問題を解決する方法
a way to solve the problem

Adjusted Expression

(この)^{かた}やり方^{つか}を使えば、^{もんだい}問題を^{かいけつ}解決できるでしょう。

Using this method, you should be able to solve the problem.

Example

^{ほうほう}この方法で^{もんだい}問題が^{かいけつ}解決できる。

This method can solve the problem.

Notes

"Houhou" is used to express a way or method to do something. The word "houhou" is a noun that means "method" or "way."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

presenting a means

explaining a method for solving a problem

sharing how to do something

Tags EN

immediate grammar

noun

method

means

problem solving

Become useful

もの 物になる

Mono ni naru

Become useful

Variants

- 物になる
become useful
- 物になった？
become practical
- ぜんぜん物にならない
amount to something

Adjusted Expression

フランス語は、ふらんすご 実用的にじつようてき 使えるつか ようになりましたか。

Has your French become practically usable?

Example

A 「フランス語、物ものになった？」 B 「いや、ぜんぜん」

A: Has your French become useful? B: No, not at all.

Notes

"Mono ni naru" means that your skills or abilities have become practical and useful. The word "mono" is a noun that means "thing," and "naru" is a verb that means "to become."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing that a skill has become practical

checking learning results

checking whether an ability has reached a usable level

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

skill

learning result

practicality

Fun

たの
楽しい

Tanoshii

Fun

Variants

- 楽しい
fun
- 楽しかった
was fun
- 楽しいですか
is it fun?

Adjusted Expression

きのう ばーてい ゆかい まんぞく
昨日のパーティーは、愉快で満足できるものでした。

Yesterday's party was enjoyable and satisfying.

Example

A 「きのうのパーティー、楽しかったね」 B 「うん、楽しかった」

A: Yesterday's party was fun. B: Yeah, it was fun.

Notes

"Tanoshii" is an i-adjective meaning "fun" or "enjoyable." I-adjectives are primarily used to express one's own feelings, and it is unnecessary to make such expressions polite. For this reason, adding the polite auxiliary

verb "desu" makes the expression sound childish. It is also uncommon to ask someone, "Tanoshii desu ka?" If it is asked, it is typically in a context where you are questioning, "Is this really fun?" - perhaps implying doubt about whether the person is genuinely having fun. In such cases, you might also confirm your assumption by saying, "It's not fun, is it?" to suggest that the other person might not be enjoying themselves either.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing enjoyment giving a positive evaluation of an experience

questioning whether someone is enjoying something

Tags EN

immediate grammar adjective emotional expression evaluative expression

i-adjective

Happy

うれしい

Ureshii

Happy

Variants

- うれしい
happy
- うれしかった
was happy
- 会えてうれしい
glad to see

Adjusted Expression

きょう きゅうゆう あ よろこ
今日、旧友に会えたことを喜んでいきます。

I am pleased that I was able to see an old friend today.

Example

きょう きゅうゆう あ
今日は旧友に会えて、うれしかった。

I was happy to see an old friend today.

Notes

"Ureshii" is an i-adjective that means "happy" or "glad." It is used to express personal joy when something positive happens or when you receive something meaningful. While similar to "tanoshii" (fun or enjoyable), they are used in different contexts. "Ureshii" describes joy

from specific events or outcomes, whereas "tanoshii" refers to pleasant feelings derived from experiences or environments.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing joy

reacting to an event or result

sharing a personal feeling

Tags EN

immediate grammar

adjective

emotional expression

joy

i-adjective

Don't look

見ないで

Minaide

Don't look

Variants

- 見ないで
don't look
- 見ないでください
please don't look
- こっちを見ないで
don't look this way

Adjusted Expression

くら暗いところでてれびテレビをみ見るのはさ避けてください。

Please avoid watching TV in the dark.

Example

くら暗いところでてれびテレビをみ見ないで。

Don't watch TV in the dark.

Notes

"Minaide" is the soft imperative form of the verb "miru" (to see).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

stopping someone's action

soft prohibition

warning or request

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

prohibition expression

request expression

negative imperative

That reminds me

そういえば

Sou ieba

That reminds me

Variants

- そういえば
that reminds me
- そういえばさ
speaking of which
- そういえば、明日
come to think of it

Adjusted Expression

いま わだい かんれん あす ゆき ふ てんきよほう い
今の話題に関連して、明日は雪が降ると天気予報で言っていた。

In relation to the current topic, the weather forecast said that it will snow tomorrow.

Example

A 「^{さいきん}最近、^{さむ}寒くなってきたね」 B 「^{あす}そういえば、^{ゆき}明日、^ふ雪、^ふ降るって
^{てんきよほう}天気予報、^い言ってたよ」

A: It's getting cold recently. B: That reminds me, the weather forecast says it will snow tomorrow.

Notes

"Souieba" means "that reminds me" or "speaking of which," and is used to introduce a thought or information related to the current topic. In contrast, "Tokorode" means "by the way" and is used to introduce a completely new topic that is unrelated to the ongoing conversation. The key difference is that "souieba" builds a connection to the previous topic, while "tokorode" shifts the conversation to an entirely different subject.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

introducing a related topic

presenting remembered information

connecting to the previous topic

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

discourse marker

topic connection

recollection

At least

すく
少なくとも

Sukunakutomo

At least

Variants

- 少なくとも
at least
- 少なくとも一つ
at least one
- 少なくとも～は
at the very least

Adjusted Expression

さいていげん ひと もんだい かいけつ
最低限、一つの問題は解決した。

At the minimum, one problem has been solved.

Example

すく ひと もんだい かいけつ
少なくとも一つ問題が解決した。

At least one problem has been solved.

Notes

"Sukunakutomo" is used to express that something is the minimum or the least. The word "sukunakutomo" is a conjunction that means "at least" or "at the very least."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing a minimum range

presenting what can be said with certainty

giving a limited evaluation of an outcome

Tags EN

immediate grammar

adverbial expression

connective expression

minimum

limitation

To be honest

しょうじき
正直なところ

Shoujiki na tokoro

To be honest

Variants

- 正直なところ
to be honest
- 正直に言うと
honestly speaking
- 正直なところ自信がない
to be honest, I'm not confident

Adjusted Expression

ほんとう きもちをい、このけいかくにはあまりじしんがありません。

If I say how I really feel, I am not very confident about this plan.

Example

しょうじき、このけいかくにはあまりじしんがありません。

To be honest, I'm not very confident about this plan.

Notes

The phrase "shoujikinatokoro" literally means "honestly speaking" or "to be honest." It is used to express the speaker's true feelings or genuine thoughts in a candid and straightforward manner. This phrase is

typically used to introduce a statement that reflects the speaker's honest opinion, real emotions, or unfiltered perspective. It can soften the impact of a direct statement, making it sound more sincere or humble.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

presenting one's true feelings

introducing a candid opinion

softening a direct statement

Tags EN

immediate grammar

formulaic expression

discourse marker

true feelings

candor

softening expression

Probably

たぶん

Tabun

Probably

Variants

- たぶん
probably
- たぶんそう
probably so
- たぶん来ない
probably won't come

Adjusted Expression

かくじつ 確実ではないが、そのかのうせい 可能性がたか 高いとおも 思う。

I am not certain, but I think that possibility is high.

Example

ひと あの人てんさい は天才だ。でも、ほんにん 本人はそれにき 気づいていない...たぶん。

That person is a genius. But he doesn't realize it... probably.

Notes

"Tabun" is an adverb that means "probably" or "likely" and is used when referring to uncertain or possible situations. It is often employed when the speaker is not completely sure about something or wants to express a prediction without sounding overly assertive. For example, in the

sentence "Tabun kare wa konai" ("He probably won't come"), the speaker conveys a belief or expectation while acknowledging a degree of uncertainty. "Tabun" is also commonly used in Japanese to soften statements, reflecting a cultural preference for indirect or less definitive expressions.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing uncertainty

avoiding a definite statement

presenting a guess

Tags EN

immediate grammar

adverb

colloquial

conjecture

uncertainty

softening expression

Soon/in the near future

ちか
近いうちに

Chikai uchi ni

Soon/in the near future

Variants

- 近いうちに
soon
- 近いうちにまた
in the near future
- 近いうちに連絡します
before long

Adjusted Expression

きんじつちゅう いっしょ しょくじ
近日中に、また一緒に食事をしましょう。

Let us have a meal together again in the near future.

Example

ちか しょくじ
近いうちに、また食事でもしましょう。

Let's have a meal together soon.

Notes

"Chikai uchi ni" is an adverbial phrase used to indicate that something will happen soon or in the near future.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing a plan in the near future

suggesting meeting or contacting again

keeping the exact timing vague

Tags EN

immediate grammar

adverbial expression

colloquial

time expression

plan

vague expression

For that reason

そういう訳わけで

Sou iu wake de

For that reason

Variants

- そういう訳で
for that reason
- そういうわけで
that's why
- まあ、そういう訳で
so, for that reason

Adjusted Expression

いじょう りゆう 以上の理由により、きょう しゅくだい ていしゅつ 今日は宿題を提出できません。

For the reasons stated above, I cannot submit my homework today.

Example

ねこ きーぼーど うえ ある まわ げんこう き 猫がキーボードの上を歩き回り、原稿が消えた。そういう訳で、今日は宿題が出せなくてすみません。

The cat walked across my keyboard and deleted my manuscript. So, I'm sorry I couldn't turn in my homework today.

Notes

"Souiu wake de" is a versatile expression in Japanese that is used to summarize reasons, excuses, or outcomes. Its meaning can shift depending on the situation, functioning as both a clumsy excuse and a lame excuse. In the case of a clumsy excuse, such as "The cat walked across my keyboard," it frames an unexpected event as the cause of a problem. While the explanation may seem a little awkward or silly, it often carries a humorous and endearing quality, inviting the listener to respond with, "Well, I guess it can't be helped." On the other hand, in the case of a lame excuse, like "Aliens stole my homework," it is used to package an obviously unconvincing or far-fetched explanation as if it were logical or believable. This flexibility allows "souiu wake de" to adapt to a wide range of situations, adding humor or charm depending on the context and the nature of the excuse.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

summarizing a reason

presenting an excuse

connecting to a result

Tags EN

immediate grammar

connective expression

discourse marker

reason explanation

excuse

humor

I'm not saying this to brag, but...

べつ じまん
別に自慢しているわけではないんですが、

Betsuni jiman shite iru wake de wa nain desu ga,

I'm not saying this to brag, but...

Variants

- 別に自慢しているわけではないんですが、
I'm not saying this to brag, but...
- 別に自慢じゃないんですが、
I'm not trying to boast, but...
- 別に自慢ってわけじゃないんだけど、
Not that I'm bragging, but...

Adjusted Expression

じまん いと ねこ め あ かくりつ たか
自慢する意図はありませんが、猫と目が合う確率が高いのです。

I do not mean to boast, but I often make eye contact with cats.

Example

べつ じまん ねこ め あ かくりつ
別に自慢しているわけではないんですが、猫と目が合う確率が(高:)いんです。

I'm not saying this to brag, but I quite often make eye contact with cats.

Notes

"Betsuni jiman shite iru wake de wa nain desu ga" is a phrase used to soften statements that might sound like boasting or self-praise. It is often

used when sharing a personal trait or experience the speaker finds amusing or interesting. The phrase acknowledges the potentially self-centered nature of the remark while adding a touch of humor to create a relaxed atmosphere. By using this phrase, the speaker can comfortably share quirky or unique anecdotes about themselves without appearing overly arrogant. That said, deep down, they might actually feel a little proud.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

softening a statement that may sound boastful

introducing a personal trait or experience modestly

self-disclosure with a touch of humor

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

prefacing expression

boast-softening expression

humor

self-disclosure

If anything happens

なんかあったら

Nanka attara

If anything happens

Variants

- なんかあったら
if anything happens
- 何かあったら
if something comes up
- なんかあったら連絡して
contact me if anything happens

Adjusted Expression

なに もんだい お ばあい れんらく
何か問題が起きた場合は、すぐに連絡してください。

If any problem occurs, please contact me immediately.

Example

なんかあったら、すぐに^{れんらく}連絡してください。

If anything happens, please contact me immediately.

Notes

"Nanka attara" is a casual phrase used to offer help if the other person needs assistance. The word "nanka" means "something" or "anything" and is often used in informal contexts to refer to unspecified things. By adding "attara," the speaker expresses readiness to help if the need

arises. This phrase is commonly used to show willingness to lend a hand in various situations, such as supporting a friend or responding to an emergency.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

offering support to someone

asking someone to contact you in an emergency

preparing for an unspecified possibility

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

considerate expression

offer of support

contact request

vague expression

Somehow it will work out

なんとかなる

Nantoka naru

Somehow it will work out

Variants

- なんとかなる
somehow it will work out
- 明日はなんとかなる
tomorrow will somehow work out
- まあ、なんとかなる
it'll work out somehow

Adjusted Expression

あす、なんらかの形で問題が解決するだろう。

Tomorrow, the problem will probably be resolved in some way.

Example

さいふが空なのに「明日はなんとかなる！」って能天気だな。

Even though his wallet is empty, he is so optimistic, saying, "Somehow it will work out tomorrow!"

Notes

"Nantoka naru" is a phrase used to express optimism or hope that things will work out somehow, even in difficult or uncertain situations. The word "nantoka" means "somehow" or "in some way," and "naru" means

"to become" or "to work out." By combining these words, the phrase conveys a sense of confidence that things will eventually fall into place, despite the current challenges or obstacles. This expression is often used to encourage oneself or others to stay positive and hopeful, even when facing adversity or uncertainty.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing an optimistic outlook

reducing anxiety

expressing weakly grounded hope

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

optimistic expression

hope

uncertainty

encouragement

Can't repay

かえ
返しきれない

Kaeshikirenai

Can't repay

Variants

- 返しきれない
can't repay
- 返しても返しきれない
can never fully repay
- 御恩は返しきれない
cannot repay the kindness

Adjusted Expression

しゃっきん かんぜん へんさい
借金を完全に返済することができない。

I cannot fully repay the debt.

Example

こうりが し かね か かえ かえ しゃっきん
高利貸とは知らずに、お金を借りて、返しても返しきれない借金になって
しまった。

I borrowed money without realizing it was from a loan shark, and now
I'm stuck with debt I can never fully repay.

Notes

"Kaeshikirenai" describes a situation where one cannot fully repay a debt or obligation. The term combines "kaesu" (to return or repay) and the negative potential form of "kiru" (to cut or finish), conveying the inability to complete repayment. This phrase often implies financial or time-related constraints and can also be used metaphorically to express the inability to reciprocate kindness or make amends. For example, it can be used in responses to deep gratitude, such as "This kindness is something I can never fully repay."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing inability to repay expressing gratitude too great to repay

expressing inability to complete an action

Tags EN

immediate grammar compound verb colloquial repayment reciprocating kindness

inability to complete

What should I do?

どうしたらいいんでしょうかねえ。

Doushitara ii n deshouka nee.

What should I do?

Variants

- どうしたらいいんでしょうかねえ。
what should I do?
- どうしたらいいんでしょうか。
what should I do about this?
- どうすればいいんでしょうか。
what would be the best thing to do?

Adjusted Expression

この状況じょうきょうにどのようたいおうに対応すればよいか、判断はんだんに迷まよっている。

I am unsure how I should deal with this situation.

Example

友達ともだちの犬いぬが、なぜか私わたしにだけ(敬語:)つかを使うんですけど、どうしたらいいんでしょうかねえ。

My friend's dog, for some reason, only uses polite/honorific language with me. What should I do?

Notes

"Doushitara ii n deshouka nee" is a phrase used to express uncertainty about a situation or to seek advice on how to handle it. "Doushitara"

means "what should be done?" or "what is the best course of action?"

When used in the full phrase "Doushitara ii n deshouka nee," it conveys a casual and slightly introspective tone. This expression is commonly used in informal conversations when discussing personal concerns or seeking advice from friends or family.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

asking how to deal with something

sharing perplexity

lightly asking for advice

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

consultative expression

perplexity

asking for advice

self-talk

May not look it, but...

ああ^み見えて、...

Aa miete, ...

May not look it, but...

Variants

- ああ見えて、...
may not look it, but...
- ああ見えて実は
it may not seem so, but...
- ああ見えて彼は
despite appearances

Adjusted Expression

がいけん 外見からは み そう見えないが、 かれ 彼には いがい 意外な のうりよく 能力がある。

Although it may not seem so from his appearance, he has an unexpected ability.

Example

ああ^み見えて、^{かれ} 彼は ^{かいしゃ} 会社で 「^{まじゅつし} Excel の魔術師」 ^よ って呼ばれてるらしい。

He may not look it, but at work, they call him the Wizard of Excel.

Notes

"Aamiete" is a phrase used to introduce surprising or unexpected facts or revelations about someone or something that may not be immediately

apparent from their appearance or behavior. Literally meaning "may not look like that," the phrase is followed by statements that contradict or cast doubt on the initial impression. This expression is often used to highlight hidden talents, unexpected skills, or surprising qualities that are not immediately obvious.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

presenting a gap between appearance and reality

introducing an unexpected fact

revealing a hidden ability

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

prefacing expression

unexpectedness

character evaluation

appearance and reality

Do over

な お
やり直す

Yarinaosu

Do over

Variants

- やり直す
do over
- 最初からやり直す
start over from scratch
- やり直し
redoing

Adjusted Expression

しっぱい さいしょ いちどおこな
失敗したので、最初からもう一度行う。

Since it failed, I will do it again from the beginning.

Example

おでんをつく なんかカレーができてた。さいしょ なお
おでんを作ってた、なぜかカレーができてた。最初からやり直そう。

I was making oden, but somehow it turned into curry. Let's start over from scratch.

Notes

"Yarinaosu" is a compound verb formed by combining the masu-form "yari" of the verb "yaru" (to do) with "naosu" (to fix), and it means "to

redo" or "to do over." It is used when starting something over from the beginning or correcting a mistake. Additionally, when nominalized as "yarinaoshi," it refers to the act of redoing itself. Oden is a traditional Japanese dish made by simmering ingredients like daikon radish, eggs, and konjac in a light dashi broth, and it is popular as a winter staple. On the other hand, curry is a spiced stew, widely enjoyed in Japan as curry rice, characterized by its uniquely sweet and savory roux. Thus, "yarinaosu" conveys the idea of retrying after failure or making a fresh start.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

retrying after failure

expressing starting over from the beginning

correcting a mistake

Tags EN

immediate grammar

compound verb

colloquial

retrying

correction

failure

I hope so, but...

そうだといいけど、

Sou da to ii kedo,

I hope so, but...

Variants

- そうだといいけど
I hope so, but...
- そうだといいんだけど
I hope it does, but...
- うまくいくといいけど
I hope it goes well, but...

Adjusted Expression

試験しけんがうまくいくことを望のぞんでいるが、勉強べんきょうしていないので不安ふあんである。

I hope the exam goes well, but I am anxious because I have not studied.

Example

A 「試験しけん、うまくいくといいね」 B 「そうだといいけど、勉強べんきょうしてないから不安ふあんだよ」

A: I hope the exam goes well. B: I hope so too, but I'm anxious because I haven't studied.

Notes

"Souda to iikedo" is a phrase used to express hope or wish for a positive outcome while acknowledging the possibility of uncertainty or anxiety.

Literally meaning "it would be good if that's the case," the phrase combines the conditional form "souda to ii" of the verb "sou da" (it is so) with "kedo" (but), creating a nuanced expression that balances optimism with realism. This phrase is often used in conversations to convey a mix of hope and concern, reflecting the speaker's desire for a favorable result while recognizing the potential for doubt or unease.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing hope and anxiety

responding with hope for a good outcome

sharing uncertainty

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

hope

anxiety

uncertainty

Indescribable

なんともいえない

Nantomoiennai

Indescribable

Variants

- なんともいえない
indescribable
- なんとも言えない
hard to describe
- なんともいえない気持ち
I can't really say

Adjusted Expression

(その)映画の結末^{けつまつ}については、簡単^{かんたん}には評価^{ひょうか}できない。

I cannot easily evaluate the ending of that movie.

Example

その映画^{えいが}の結末^{けつまつ}はなんともいえない。

The ending of the movie is indescribable.

Notes

"Nantomoiennai" is a phrase used to describe something that is difficult to express in words or that defies explanation. It is often used when encountering complex emotions or situations that are hard to describe or when it is better not to say anything when asked for an opinion.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing a feeling that is hard to put into words

expressing complex emotion

avoiding a clear judgment

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

emotional expression

vague expression

suspending judgment

That seems to be the case

そのようですね。

Sono you desu ne.

That seems to be the case

Variants

- そのようですね。
that seems to be the case
- そのようです。
it seems so
- どうやらそのようですね。
apparently, that seems to be the case

Adjusted Expression

あいて かんさつ じょうきょう あ
相手の観察は、状況に合っているようだ。

The other person's observation appears to fit the situation.

Example

A 「このカフェ、最近人気みたいです」 B 「そのようですね、いつも混んでいる気がします」

A: This cafe seems to be popular lately. B: That seems to be the case; it always seems crowded.

Notes

"Sonoyoudesune" is a phrase used to acknowledge or agree with a statement made by someone else. It is often used to express agreement or

confirmation with the speaker's observation, opinion, or assessment. The phrase "sono you" means "that way" or "like that," and "desu ne" is a polite ending that adds a sense of agreement or affirmation. By combining these elements, the phrase conveys a sense of understanding or recognition of the situation described by the other person. This expression is commonly used in conversations to show attentiveness, agreement, or shared perception with the speaker.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

agreeing with someone's observation

sharing recognition of the situation

polite confirmation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

polite expression

response expression

agreement

confirmation

situational recognition

Is it a big deal?

そんなにさわぐことですか。

Sonnani sawagu koto desu ka.

Is it a big deal?

Variants

- そんなにさわぐことですか。
is it a big deal?
- そんなに騒ぐことですか。
is it something to make such a fuss about?
- そんなに大騒ぎすることですか。
is it worth making that much noise about?

Adjusted Expression

その状じょうきょう況は、それほどおお大きなもんだい問題ではない。

The situation is not such a serious problem.

Example

A 「何かなに問題もんだいが起きたのかな」 B 「そんなにさわぐことですか。ただつか疲れているだけです」

A: I wonder if something happened. B: Is it a big deal? I'm just tired.

Notes

"Sonnani sawagu koto desuka" is a phrase used to question the importance or necessity of making a big fuss about something. "Sonnani" means "to that extent" or "so much," and "sawagu" means "to make

noise" or "to cause a disturbance." By combining these elements, the phrase conveys a sense of questioning the significance or need to make excessive noise or fuss about something. This expression is often used to express skepticism about excessive criticism or overblown claims made by others.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

questioning an overreaction lightly protesting excessive fuss

denying the seriousness of the situation

Tags EN

immediate grammar colloquial question expression protest overreaction

evaluative expression

I brought everything

ぜんぶもった。

Zenbu motta.

I brought everything.

Variants

- ぜんぶもった。
I brought everything.
- 全部持った。
I have everything.
- 必要なものは全部持った。
I brought everything I need.

Adjusted Expression

ひつよう も もの
必要な持ち物は、すべて持っている。

I have all the necessary belongings.

Example

A 「わす忘れ物、ない？」 B 「ぜんぶもった」

A: Got everything? B: I brought everything.

Notes

"Zenbu motta" is a phrase used to indicate that one has brought or obtained everything that is needed or required. "Zenbu" means "everything" or "all," and "motta" is the past tense of the verb "motteru" (to have or to bring). In Japanese, the past tense can be used to describe a

current state or situation. This expression is commonly used to convey that one has all the necessary items or has completed a task by bringing everything required.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

responding to a belongings check

reporting that one has everything needed

checking before leaving

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

belongings check

ready to go

My pleasure

よろこんで

Yorokonde

My pleasure

Variants

- よろこんで
my pleasure
- はい、よろこんで
gladly
- よろこんでお手伝いします
I'd be happy to help

Adjusted Expression

てっだ しょうだく
手伝うことを承諾している。

The speaker is accepting the request to help.

Example

A 「てっだ手伝ってくれませんか？」 B 「よろこんで」

A: Can you help me? B: My pleasure.

Notes

"Yorokonde" is a phrase used to express willingness or joy in helping or assisting someone. It is the te-form of the verb "yorokobu" (to be pleased or delighted) and is used in this context to convey a sense of joy or satisfaction in helping others. However, it can also be used in situations

where one may not be able to help with joy but is willing to assist. If the help can be done in a moment and is unavoidable, one might say this. If someone is asking for help while you are busy working, that is their problem.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

responding to a request for help

showing willingness to cooperate

positive acceptance

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

acceptance

cooperation

considerate expression

Better than nothing

しないよりまし

Shinai yori mashi

Better than nothing

Variants

- しないよりまし
better than nothing
- 何もしないよりまし
better than doing nothing
- やらないよりまし
better than not doing it

Adjusted Expression

なにもしないよりは、すこ少しでも勉強べんきょうした方がよい。ほう

It is better to study even a little than to do nothing.

Example

A 「いま今から試験勉強しけんべんきょうですか？」 B 「ええ、しないよりまし」

A: Are you going to study for the exam now? B: Yes, better than nothing.

Notes

"Shinai yori mashi" is a phrase used to express that doing something is better than doing nothing at all. The word "shinai" is the negative form of the verb "suru" (to do), and "mashi" is the comparative form of the

adjective "ii" (good). It conveys the idea that taking action is preferable to inaction. In many cases, such people may be well-prepared.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

affirming minimal action

expressing doing something despite insufficiency

reluctant positivity

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

comparative expression

minimum

action

Is it okay later?

あとでもいい？

Ato demo ii?

Is it okay later?

Variants

- あとでもいい？
is it okay later?
- あとでいい？
can I do it later?
- あとじゃだめ？
would later be okay?

Adjusted Expression

しよつき あら 食器を洗うのは、いま ではなく 後も よいか。

Would it be acceptable to wash the dishes later rather than now?

Example

A 「^{しよつき}食器^{あら}洗ってくれた？」 B 「うーん、あとでもいい？^{いま}今、^{いぬ}犬と^{あそ}遊んでるところなんだ」

A: Did you wash the dishes? B: Hmm, can I do it later? I'm playing with the dog right now.

Notes

"Ato demo ii?" is a phrase used to ask if something can be done at a different time. "Ato" means "later" or "after," and "demo" is a particle that

indicates a conditional or alternative situation. This expression is commonly used in casual conversations to check if delaying a task or changing a schedule would cause inconvenience or confusion. However, people who say this often don't do it later.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

checking whether an action can be delayed

postponing a response to a request

giving a reason not to do it now

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

postponement

responding to a request

deferral

There's no way I'd forget

わす
忘れるわけない

Wasureru wake nai

There's no way I'd forget

Variants

- 忘れるわけない
there's no way I'd forget
- 忘れるわけないでしょ
of course I remember
- 忘れるはずがない
I couldn't possibly forget

Adjusted Expression

あす かいぎ 明日の会議については、
かくじつ おぼ 確実に覚えている。

I definitely remember tomorrow's meeting.

Example

A 「あす かいぎ 明日、会議だよな？」 B 「わすれるわけないでしょ！っていうか、もう
じゅんび 準備できてるし」

A: We have a meeting tomorrow, right? B: There's no way I'd forget!
Besides, I'm already prepared.

Notes

"Wasureru wake nai" is a phrase used to express certainty or confidence that one has not forgotten something. The word "wasureru" means "to forget," and "wake nai" is a phrase that indicates the absence of a reason or cause.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

strongly denying having forgotten

reacting to someone's confirmation

expressing confidence or light pushback

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

negation

memory

pushback

Anytime

いつでもどうぞ

Itsudemo douzo

Anytime

Variants

- いつでもどうぞ
anytime
- 質問はいつでもどうぞ
feel free to ask anytime
- いつでも聞いてください
please ask anytime

Adjusted Expression

じゅぎょう 授業について しつもん 質問がある ばあい 場合は、いつでも しつもん 質問してください。

If you have any questions about the class, please ask at any time.

Example

じゅぎょう 授業について しつもん 質問がある かた 方は、いつでもどうぞ

If you have any questions about the class, feel free to ask anytime.

Notes

"Itsu demo douzo" is a phrase used to encourage someone to take action or make a request at any time. "Itsu demo" means "anytime" or "whenever," and "douzo" is an invitation or permission to do something.

However, it doesn't mean you can do it anytime without making an appointment.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

encouraging questions or consultation

giving permission or invitation

expressing openness at any time

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

considerate expression

permission expression

invitation expression

encouraging questions

I don't mind at all

まったく^き気にならない

Mattaku ki ni naranai

I don't mind at all

Variants

- まったく気にならない

I don't mind at all

- 全然気にならない

it doesn't bother me at all

- まったく気にならないよ

I don't notice it at all

Adjusted Expression

かみがた しつぱい み とく もんだい かん
髪型の失敗は、見ても特に問題だとは感じない。

I do not feel that the hairstyle mistake is a particular problem when I look at it.

Example

A 「ちょっと髪型^{かみがたしつぱい}失敗しちゃったかも」 B 「いやいや、全然^{ぜんぜんに}似合ってるし、まったく^き気にならないよ」

A: I might have messed up my hairstyle a bit. B: No, not at all. It suits you, and it doesn't bother me at all.

Notes

"Mattaku ki ni naranai" is a phrase used to express that one doesn't mind or is not bothered by something. The word "mattaku" means "completely" or "totally," and "ki ni naranai" means "not to mind" or "not to be concerned." It may be a complete failure, but if you don't say it, it may not be noticed. If you say, "I might have messed up my hairstyle," others might notice it. In general, people don't care about others as much as they think they do.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

easing someone's worry expressing that one is not bothered

expressing that a mistake is not noticeable

Tags EN

immediate grammar colloquial response expression considerate expression

easing anxiety appearance

A little too much

ちよつと^い言いすぎ

Chotto ii sugi

A little too much

Variants

- ちよつと言いすぎ
a little too much
- 言いすぎじゃない？
isn't that going a little too far?
- それは言いすぎ
that's saying too much

Adjusted Expression

あいて はつげん じじつ つよ ひょうげん
相手の発言は、事実よりも強く表現されている。

The other person's statement is expressed more strongly than the facts support.

Example

A 「あなたって、いつも何も^{なに}考えてないよね」 B 「え、それはちよつと^い言いすぎじゃない？ ちゃんと^{かんが}考えてるよ」

A: You never think about anything, do you? B: Huh, isn't that going a little too far? I do think things through.

Notes

"Chotto ii sugi" is an expression used to indicate that a statement or action is slightly exaggerated or overly extreme. The word "chotto" means "a little" or "slightly," and "iisugi" is the masu-form of the verb "iu" (to say) combined with the masu-form of "sugiru" (to exceed), meaning "saying too much." It can be used in both negative and positive contexts.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

reacting to an overstatement

light protest

softening the strength of someone's statement

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

protest

overstatement

softening expression

Do you think so?

おも
そう思うの？

Sou omou no?

Do you think so?

Variants

- そう思うの？
do you think so?
- 本当にそう思うの？
do you really think so?
- そう思う？
you think so?

Adjusted Expression

あいて かんが かくにん
相手がそのように考えているのかを確認している。

The speaker is checking whether the other person thinks that way.

Example

A 「この映画、結構面白かったよね」 B 「そう思うの？ 私はちょっと退屈だったな」

A: This movie was pretty interesting, wasn't it? B: Do you think so? I found it a bit boring.

Notes

"Sou omou no?" is a phrase used to ask for confirmation with someone's opinion or statement. The word "sou" means "that way." "Omou" is the verb "to think," and "no" is a sentence-ending particle that seeks confirmation or agreement. This expression is commonly used in conversations to check if the listener shares the speaker's perspective or to prompt further discussion about differing opinions.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

confirming someone's opinion

presenting a difference of opinion

prompting further explanation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

question expression

confirmation

opinion

difference of opinion

I have no idea

まったくわかりません。

Mattaku wakarimasen

I have no idea

Variants

- まったくわかりません。
I have no idea.
- 全然わかりません。
I don't understand at all.
- どこから始めればいいのかわかりません。
I don't know where to start.

Adjusted Expression

もんだい と かた 問題の解き方を、まったく りかい 理解できていない。

I do not understand at all how to solve the problem.

Example

A 「もんだい 問題、と 解けそうですか？」 B 「まったくわかりません。どこから はじ 始めればいいのか」

A: Do you think you can solve the problem? B: I have no idea. I don't know where to start.

Notes

"Mattaku wakarimasen" is a phrase used to express complete lack of understanding or knowledge about a particular topic or situation. The

word "mattaku" means "completely" or "totally," "wakarimasen" is the negative form of the verb "wakaru" (to understand), and it means "I don't understand."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing complete lack of understanding

showing perplexity about a problem

prefacing a request for help or explanation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

lack of understanding

perplexity

learning situation

There's nothing I can do

どうしようもない

Doushiyou mo nai

There's nothing I can do

Variants

- どうしようもない
there's nothing I can do
- どうしようもないですね
there's nothing we can do
- あの人はどうしようもない
that person is hopeless

Adjusted Expression

でんしゃでんしゃが止とまっているので、こちらで対応たいおうできることはない。

Since the train has stopped, there is nothing we can do about it.

Example

でんしゃでんしゃが止とまっている以上いじょう、どうしようもないですね。

Since the train has stopped, there's nothing we can do.

Notes

"Doushiyou mo nai" is a phrase used to express a situation where there is no solution or remedy available. The word "dou" means "how," and "shiyou" is the volitional form of the verb "suru" (to do). The phrase can be used to describe a situation where there is no solution or treatment

available, and it can also be used to describe a person as in "ano hito wa doushiyou mo nai" (That person is hopeless).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing that there is no solution

accepting the situation

negative evaluation of a person

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

evaluative expression

resignation

no solution

character evaluation

I can't stand it

がまんできない

Gaman dekinai

I can't stand it

Variants

- がまんできない
I can't stand it
- 我慢できない
I can't tolerate it
- もう我慢できない
I can't put up with it anymore

Adjusted Expression

あの芸能人の話し方に、強い不快感を覚える。

I feel strong discomfort with the way that celebrity talks.

Example

あの芸能人の話し方はがまんできない。

I can't stand the way that celebrity talks.

Notes

"Gaman dekinai" is a phrase used to express that one cannot tolerate or endure a particular situation, behavior, or person. The word "gaman" means "patience" or "endurance," and "dekinai" is the negative form of the verb "dekiru" (to be able to do). This phrase is commonly used to

convey a sense of frustration, annoyance, or exasperation when faced with something that is difficult to bear or put up with.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing inability to tolerate something

expressing discomfort

expressing strong irritation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

emotional expression

discomfort

irritation

aversion

Sorry for the trouble

めいわく
ご迷惑

Gomeiwaku

Trouble

Variants

- ご迷惑
trouble
- ご迷惑をおかけしました
sorry for the trouble
- ご迷惑をおかけして申し訳ありません
I apologize for the inconvenience

Adjusted Expression

れんらく 連絡できなかつたことで、あいて 相手に 不便 をかけたことを しゃざい 謝罪している。

The speaker is apologizing for causing inconvenience by not being able to contact the other person.

Example

しばらく、れんらく ご連絡できず、めいわく ご迷惑をおかけしました。

I'm sorry for the trouble I caused by not being able to contact you for a while.

Notes

"Gomeiwaku" is a phrase used to express an apology or regret for causing inconvenience, trouble, or annoyance to someone. The word "go" is a prefix that adds a sense of respect or formality, and "meiwaku" means "trouble" or "annoyance."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

apologizing for causing trouble

expressing that one caused inconvenience

polite apology

Tags EN

immediate grammar

polite expression

apology expression

trouble

considerate expression

formulaic expression

About how much is it?

だいたいいくらですか。

Daitai ikura desu ka.

About how much is it?

Variants

- だいたいいくらですか。
about how much is it?
- おおよそいくらですか。
approximately how much is it?
- 参加費はだいたいいくらですか？
about how much is the participation fee?

Adjusted Expression

さんかひ がいさん
参加費の概算を教えてくださいませんか。

Could you please tell me the approximate cost of the participation fee?

Example

さんかひ
参加費はだいたいいくらですか？

About how much is the participation fee?

Notes

"Daitai ikura desuka" is a phrase used to ask for an approximate or general price or cost of something. The word "daitai" means "about" or "approximately," "ikura" means "how much," and "desuka" is a polite ending that forms a question.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

asking for an approximate amount

checking the cost

checking information before joining

Tags EN

immediate grammar

polite expression

question expression

price expression

approximation

cost check

Does it suit me?

にあ
似合っていますか。

Niatte imasu ka.

Does it suit me?

Variants

- 似合っていますか。
does it suit me?
- この服、似合っていますか。
does this outfit suit me?
- 似合ってますか。
does it look good on me?

Adjusted Expression

この服は私わたしににあ似合っていますか。

Does this outfit suit me?

Example

この服、にあ似合っていますか。

Does this outfit suit me?

Notes

"Niatte imasuka" is a phrase used to ask if something looks good or suits someone. "Niau" is the verb "to suit" or "to look good," and "imasuka" is a question form indicating the current state. This expression is commonly

used to ask for others' opinions on how one looks when trying on clothes, accessories, or hairstyles.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

asking for an opinion about appearance

checking clothing or hairstyle

asking for someone's evaluation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

polite expression

question expression

appearance

evaluative expression

clothing

Let's give it a try

とりあえずやってみましょう。

Toriaezu yatte mimashou

Let's just try it for now

Variants

- とりあえずやってみましょう。
Let's just try it for now.
- とりあえず、やってみましょう。
Let's give it a try for now.
- とりあえず作ってみましょうか。
For now, let's try making it.

Adjusted Expression

結果けっかを深くふか考えかんがすぎず、まずため試しじっこうに実行してみましょう。

Without thinking too much about the outcome, let's first try doing it.

Example

A 「この料理りょうり、難むずかしそうですね」 B 「とりあえず、作つくってみましょうか」

A: This dish looks difficult. B: Let's just try making it for now.

Notes

"Toriaezu yatte mimashou" is a phrase used to suggest trying something as a first step or temporarily without worrying about the outcome. The word "toriaezu" means "for now" or "first of all," "yatte" is the te-form of the verb "yaru" (to do), and "mimashou" is the volitional form of the verb

"miru" (to see or try). This expression is commonly used to encourage taking action or making an attempt without overthinking or hesitating.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

encouraging action for the time being

suggesting trying something out

prompting someone to start without overthinking

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

suggestion expression

encouraging action

trying

for now

Either is fine

どっちでもいい

Docchi demo ii

Either is fine

Variants

- どっちでもいい
either is fine
- どっちでもいいですよ
either one is fine
- どちらでもいいです
either would be fine

Adjusted Expression

すしでも ちゅうかでも、どちらを えらんで もんだいも問題ない。

There is no problem with choosing either sushi or Chinese food.

Example

A 「すしにしますか、ちゅうかにしますか」 B 「どっちでもいいですよ」

A: Would you like sushi or Chinese food? B: Either is fine.

Notes

"Docchi demo ii" is a phrase used to express that either option is acceptable or suitable. The word "docchi" means "which" or "either," "demo" is a particle that means "or," and "ii" means "good" or "fine." This

expression is commonly used to indicate that one has no preference between two or more options or that both options are equally acceptable.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing no strong preference between options

leaving the choice to the other person

expressing that either option is acceptable

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

choice

no preference

considerate expression

I'll leave it up to you

おまかせします。

Omakase shimasu.

I'll leave it up to you

Variants

- おまかせします。
I'll leave it up to you.
- お任せします。
I'll leave it to you.
- おまかせでお願いします。
I'll let you decide.

Adjusted Expression

きょう ばんごはん めにゅー
今日の晩御飯のメニュー、おまかせします。

I'll leave the menu for tonight's dinner up to you.

Example

A 「今日の晩御飯、何にしようかな」 B 「おまかせします」

A: What should we have for dinner tonight? B: I'll leave it up to you.

Notes

"Omakase shimasu" is a phrase used to express that one is entrusting a decision or task to someone else. The word "omakase" means "to entrust" or "to leave it up to someone," and "shimasu" is the polite form of the verb "suru" (to do). This expression is commonly used to delegate

responsibility or decision-making to another person and is often used in situations where one is unsure or has no preference.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

entrusting judgment to someone else

leaving the choice to someone else

expressing no particular preference

Tags EN

immediate grammar

polite expression

response expression

entrusting

choice

no preference

Is that on purpose?

わざとですか。

Wazato desu ka.

Is that on purpose?

Variants

- わざとですか。
is that on purpose?
- それ、わざとですか？
did you do that on purpose?
- わざとやったんですか？
was that intentional?

Adjusted Expression

プリン、間違^{まちが}えて食^たべたのは、わざとなんですか？

Did you eat the pudding on purpose by mistake?

Example

A 「プリン、間違^{まちが}えて食^たべちゃった」 B 「それ、わざとですか？」

A: I accidentally ate the pudding. B: Did you do that on purpose?

Notes

"Wazato desuka" is a phrase used to ask if someone did something intentionally or deliberately. The word "wazato" means "on purpose" or "intentionally," and "desuka" is a polite ending that forms a question. This expression is commonly used to clarify someone's intentions or motives

when their actions or words seem suspicious or unusual. In most cases, it's on purpose. Normally, you wouldn't eat someone else's pudding by mistake if you didn't buy it yourself.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

checking whether an action was intentional

doubting someone's excuse

light criticism

Tags EN

immediate grammar

polite expression

question expression

checking intention

doubt

criticism

If you think you can do it, give it a try

やれるものなら、やってみろ。

Yareru mono nara, yatte miro.

If you think you can do it, give it a try

Variants

- やれるものなら、やってみろ。
if you think you can do it, give it a try
- できるものなら、やってみろ。
go ahead, if you can
- やれるなら、やってみろ。
try it, if you can

Adjusted Expression

そんなに自信じしんがあるなら、では、やってみせていただきますでしょうか？

If you are so confident, then shall we see you do it?

Example

A 「今日きょうこそ俺おれたちが勝かつからな！」 B 「ふん、やれるものなら、やってみろ！」

A: Today, we're going to win! B: Hmph, if you think you can do it, give it a try!

Notes

"Yareru mono nara, yatte miro" is a phrase used to challenge someone to take action or make an attempt if they believe they are capable of doing

so. The word "yareru" means "to be able to do," "mono" means "thing," "nara" is a conditional form that means "if," and "yatte miro" is a phrase that means "give it a try." This expression is commonly used to provoke or challenge someone to test their abilities or skills.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

provoking the other person

challenging someone to test their ability

expressing strong rivalry

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

provocative expression

imperative expression

rivalry

competition

It'll be all right

だいじょうぶ
きっと大丈夫

Kitto daijoubu

It'll be all right

Variants

- きっと大丈夫
it'll be all right
- きっと大丈夫だよ
I'm sure it'll be fine
- 大丈夫だよ
it'll be okay

Adjusted Expression

A 「大丈夫だいじょうぶでしょうか？」 B 「ええ、おそらく、大丈夫だいじょうぶじゃないでしょうか」

A: Do you think it'll be all right? B: Yes, I think it'll probably be fine.

Example

A 「大丈夫だいじょうぶかな？」 B 「きっと大丈夫だいじょうぶだよ」

A: I wonder if it's okay? B: I'm sure it'll be fine.

Notes

"Daijoubu" is a versatile Japanese word that can be used in various situations to express that everything is okay, fine, or safe. It can be used

to reassure someone, confirm that something is acceptable, or indicate that there is no problem.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

reassuring someone

expressing expectation of a good outcome

responding to anxiety

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

reassurance

encouragement

easing anxiety

I couldn't do anything

なに
何もできなかつた

Nani mo dekinakatta

I couldn't do anything

Variants

- 何もできなかつた
I couldn't do anything
- 今日は何もできなかつた
I couldn't get anything done today
- 忙しくて何もできなかつた
I was too busy to do anything

Adjusted Expression

きょう よてい
今日は予定していたことを、ほとんど進めることができませんでした。

Today, I was hardly able to make progress on what I had planned.

Example

きょう いそが なに
今日忙しくて、何もできなかつた。

I was so busy today that I couldn't do anything.

Notes

"Nani mo dekinakatta" is a phrase used to express that one was unable to do anything due to various reasons such as being busy, lacking the ability, or facing obstacles. The word "nani" means "what," "mo" is a

particle that means "anything," and "dekinakatta" is the past negative form of the verb "dekiru" (to be able to do).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

looking back on the day

expressing lack of accomplishment due to busyness

expressing slight disappointment about not getting things done

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

emotional expression

lack of accomplishment

busyness

looking back

I don't know what's going on

わけわからん

Wake wakaran

I don't know what's going on

Variants

- わけわからん
I don't know what's going on
- わけがわからない
I don't understand what's happening
- もうわけわからん
this makes no sense

Adjusted Expression

この^{すうがく}数学の^{もんだい}問題は、^{こうしき}公式が^でたくさん出てくるので、^{ないよう}内容を^{りかい}理解するのが^{むづか}難しいことばかりです。

This math problem has so many formulas that it is difficult to understand what is going on.

Example

この^{すうがく}数学の^{もんだい}問題、^{こうしき}公式が^でたくさん出てきてわけわからん！

There are so many formulas in this math problem that I don't know what's going on!

Notes

"Wake ga wakaranai" is a phrase used to express that one doesn't understand the reason or cause of something. The word "wake" means "reason" or "cause," "ga" is a particle that marks the subject of the sentence, and "wakaranai" is the negative form of the verb "wakaru" (to understand).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing lack of understanding

expressing confusion

reacting to complexity

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

emotional expression

confusion

lack of understanding

learning situation

I can't anymore

もう無理むり

Mou muri

I can't anymore

Variants

- もう無理
I can't anymore
- もう無理です
I can't do any more
- これ以上は無理
I have reached my limit

Adjusted Expression

A 「もう一杯いっばい、いかがですか？」 B 「ありがとうございます。ただ、これ以上いじょうは控えておきます。明日あしたに差し支えさつかるといけませんので」

A: How about one more drink? B: Thank you, but I will stop here. I do not want it to affect me tomorrow.

Example

A 「もう一杯いっばい、いかがですか？」 B 「もう無理むり、どうもありがとう。これ以上いじょうの飲んだら明日あしたが大変たいへんだから」

A: How about one more drink? B: I can't anymore, thank you. If I drink any more, tomorrow's going to be rough.

Notes

"Mou muri" is a phrase used to express that one has reached their limit or cannot continue due to exhaustion, fatigue, or difficulty. The word "mou" means "already" or "anymore," and "muri" means "impossible" or "unbearable."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing that one has reached a limit

expressing inability to continue any further

declining someone's offer

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

response expression

limit

refusal

eating and drinking situation

What do you think from your standpoint?

たなか てき
田中さんの^{てき}的にはどうですか。

Tanaka-san teki ni wa dou desu ka.

What do you think from your standpoint?

Variants

- 田中さんの^{てき}的にはどうですか。
what do you think from your standpoint?
- あなたの^{てき}的にはどうですか。
how does it look to you?
- 先生の^{てき}的にはどうですか。
what is your take on it?

Adjusted Expression

A 「この^{ていあん}提案^{さんせい}には賛成ですか？」 B 「田中^{たなか}さんのお立^{たちば}場では、どのよう^{かんが}にお考
えですか」

A: Do you agree with this proposal? B: From your standpoint, Tanaka-san, what do you think?

Example

A 「この^{ていあん}提案^{さんせい}、賛成ですか？」 B 「田中^{たなか}さん^{てき}的にはどうですか」

A: Do you agree with this proposal? B: What do you think from your standpoint, Tanaka-san?

Notes

"Teki ni wa dou desuka" is a phrase used to ask for someone's opinion or perspective on a particular topic or situation. The word "teki" means "-like" or "-ish," "ni" is a particle that indicates the target or recipient of an action, "wa" is a particle that marks the topic of the sentence, and "dou desuka" is a phrase that means "how is it?" or "what do you think?" This expression is commonly used to inquire about someone's thoughts, feelings, or reactions based on their personal viewpoint or standpoint.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

asking for an opinion from the other person's standpoint

directing the judgment to the other person

checking a personal view

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

question expression

checking opinion

standpoint

informal usage

In my own way

ぼくはぼくなり

Boku wa boku nari ni

In my own way

Variants

- ぼくはぼくなり
in my own way
- 私は私なりに
in a way that makes sense to me
- 自分なりに
according to my own approach

Adjusted Expression

A 「この問題^{もんだい}は、どのように解^ときますか」 B 「私は、自分の考え^{かんが}方^{かた}に基^{もと}づいて
検^{けん}討^{とう}してみます」

A: How would you solve this problem? B: I will examine it based on my own way of thinking.

Example

A 「この問題^{もんだい}、どうやって解^とく？」 B 「ぼくはぼくなり^{かんが}に考^{かんが}えてみるよ」

A: How do you solve this problem? B: I'll think about it in my own way.

Notes

"Boku wa boku nari ni" is a phrase used to express that one does things according to one's own beliefs, values, or preferences. The word "boku"

means "I" or "me," "wa" is a particle that marks the topic of the sentence, "nari" means "in one's own way," and "ni" is a particle that indicates the method or manner of doing something. This expression is commonly used to convey that one has one's own approach or perspective on a particular matter or situation. "Boku" is generally used by male speakers. Female speakers commonly use "watashi."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing one's own way of doing something

presenting one's own way of thinking

stating an approach different from someone else's

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

self-expression

method

viewpoint

individual difference

Many people

おお ひと
多くの人

Ooku no hito

Many people

Variants

- 多くの人
many people
- 多くの人は
many people think so
- 多くの人がそう思っている
a lot of people think so

Adjusted Expression

おお ひと かんが おも
多くの人が、そのように考えていると思われます。

It seems that many people think that way.

Example

おお ひと おも
多くの人はそう思っている。

Many people think so.

Notes

"Ooku no hito" is a phrase used to refer to many people in a group or population. The word "ooku" means "many" or "a lot," "no" is a particle that indicates association, and "hito" means "people" or "person." This

expression is commonly used to make generalizations or statements about what many people think, believe, or do. A similar word is "ooi," which is an i-adjective, but be careful, as there is no expression like "ooi hito."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing a general tendency

presenting the opinion of many people

expressing a view close to the majority

Tags EN

immediate grammar

noun phrase

quantity expression

generalization

stating an opinion

What do you think?

どうおも思いますか。

Dou omoimasu ka.

What do you think?

Variants

- どう思いますか。
what do you think?
- どう思う？
what do you think about it?
- この問題、どう思いますか？
what is your opinion?

Adjusted Expression

A 「この問題もんだいについて、どのようにお考えかんがですか」 B 「かなり難むずかしい問題もんだいだと
おもおもいます」

A: What are your thoughts on this problem? B: I think it is quite a difficult problem.

Example

A 「この問題もんだい、どうおもおもいますか？」 B 「難むずかしいですね」

A: What do you think about this problem? B: It's difficult.

Notes

"Dou omou" is a phrase used to ask for someone's opinion, thoughts, or feelings about a particular topic or situation. The word "dou" means "how" or "what," and "omou" means "to think" or "to feel." This expression is commonly used to inquire about someone's perspective, viewpoint, or reaction to a specific matter or issue. You can ask someone close to you with a short "dou omou."

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

asking for someone's opinion

checking someone's thoughts or impressions

inviting someone into a discussion

Tags EN

immediate grammar

polite expression

question expression

checking opinion

impression

discussion

I have no idea

けんとう
見当もつきません

Kentou mo tsukimasen

I have no idea

Variants

- 見当もつきません

I have no idea

- まったく見当がつきません

I have absolutely no idea

- 理由は見当もつきません

I have no clue why

Adjusted Expression

なん 何でみなさんがなら並んでいるのか、りゆう理由をすいそく推測することができません。

I cannot guess the reason why everyone is lining up.

Example

なん 何でみんななら並んでいるのか、けんとう見当もつきません。

I have no idea why everyone is lining up.

Notes

"Kentou mo tsukimasen" is a phrase used to express that one has no idea, clue, or estimate about something. The word "kentou" means "idea" or "guess," "mo" is a particle that means "even," and "tsukimasen" is the

negative form of the verb "tsuku" (to attach or estimate). This expression is commonly used to convey a lack of knowledge, understanding, or insight about a particular topic or situation.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing that one does not know the reason

expressing that one has no clue

showing perplexity about a situation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

polite expression

response expression

lack of understanding

inability to guess

perplexity

Whose is that?

それは^{だれ}誰の？

Sore wa dare no?

Whose is that?

Variants

- それは誰の？
whose is that?
- これは誰の？
whose is this?
- この傘、誰の？
whose umbrella is this?

Adjusted Expression

A 「この^{かさ}傘は、どなたのものですか」 B 「あ、それは^{わたし}私のものです」

A: Whose umbrella is this? B: Oh, that is mine.

Example

A 「この^{かさ}傘、^{だれ}誰の？」 B 「あ、それ、^{わたし}私の」

A: Whose umbrella is this? B: Oh, that's mine.

Notes

"Sore wa dare no" is a phrase used to ask who something belongs to or who is responsible for something. The word "sore" means "that," "wa" is a

particle that marks the topic of the sentence, "dare" means "who," and "no" is a particle that indicates possession or association.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

asking who something belongs to

checking the owner

checking a lost or shared item

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

question expression

possession

checking ownership

elliptical expression

How was it?

どうだった

Dou datta

How was it?

Variants

- どうだった
how was it?
- 映画、どうだった？
how was the movie?
- どうでしたか？
how did it go?

Adjusted Expression

A 「映画えいがを見た感想かんそうはどうでしたか」 B 「面白おもしろかったです」

A: What did you think of the movie? B: It was interesting.

Example

A 「映画えいが、どうだった？」 B 「面白おもしろかったよ」

A: How was the movie? B: It was interesting.

Notes

"Dou datta" is a phrase used to ask about someone's experience, impression, or opinion of something. The word "dou" means "how," and "datta" is the past form of the verb "da" (to be). A short phrase like "dou datta" is one of the fundamental techniques for improving your Japanese

skills. It is useful to use many short, simple phrases that can be said in one breath.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

asking about someone's experience or impression

asking for someone's reaction

question for continuing a conversation

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

question expression

impression

experience

conversation continuation

I can't easily fall asleep

なかなかねむ眠れない

Nakanaka nemurenai

I can't easily fall asleep

Variants

- なかなか眠れない

I can't easily fall asleep

- 最近なかなか眠れない

I have trouble falling asleep lately

- 寝つけない

I can't get to sleep

Adjusted Expression

さいきん 最近、ね寝つくまでにじかん時間がかかることがおほ多いんです。

Lately, it often takes me a long time to fall asleep.

Example

さいきん 最近、なかなかねむ眠れないんです。

Lately, I have trouble falling asleep.

Notes

"Nakanaka nemurenai" is a phrase used to express that one has difficulty falling asleep or sleeping well. The word "nakanaka" means "not easily"

or "not readily," and "nemurenai" is the negative potential form of the verb "nemuru" (to fall asleep).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing difficulty falling asleep

sharing a recent physical or lifestyle condition

talking about a problem

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

state expression

sleep

problem

physical condition

Once involved, see it through

の
乗りかかった船ふね

Norikakatta fune

Once involved, see it through

Variants

- 乗りかかった船
once involved, see it through
- 乗りかかった船だし
now that I'm involved, I have to see it through
- 乗りかかった船だから
I can't back out now

Adjusted Expression

かれ たの ぶろじえくと さんか いじょう とちゅう さいご
彼に頼まれてプロジェクトに参加した以上、途中でやめるのではなく、最後まで
せきにん も つづ おも
で責任を持って続けるべきだと思います。

Since I agreed to join the project after he asked me, I think I should not quit halfway but continue responsibly until the end.

Example

かれ たの ぶろじえくと さんか とちゅう
彼に頼まれてプロジェクトに参加したけれど、途中でやめるわけにはいかな
の
い。乗りかかった船ふねだし、最後までやるしかない。さいご

I was asked by him to join the project, but I can't quit halfway. Now that I'm involved, I have no choice but to see it through to the end.

Notes

The Japanese idiom "norikakatta fune" means being halfway into something and unable to back out, so you must see it through.

"Norikakatta" comes from the verb "norikakaru," where "noru" means "to get on" (for example, a boat) and "kakaru" describes an incomplete or ongoing state. While it may look similar to "be in the same boat," "norikakatta fune" emphasizes personal responsibility after becoming involved, whereas "be in the same boat" highlights shared circumstances or solidarity.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing that one cannot quit halfway

expressing the need to see something through after becoming involved

expressing responsibility

Tags EN

immediate grammar

idiomatic expression

colloquial

responsibility

continuation

joining midway

Do you want a little more?

もうちょっとい要りますか。

Mou chotto irimasu ka.

Do you want a little more?

Variants

- もうちょっと要りますか。
do you want a little more?
- もう少し要りますか。
would you like a little more?
- コーヒー、もう少し要りますか。
would you like some more coffee?

Adjusted Expression

A 「こーひーをもう少しすこお注つぎしましょうか」 B 「いいえ、じゅうぶん十分いただきました。ありがとうございます」

A: Would you like me to pour you a little more coffee? B: No, I have had enough. Thank you.

Example

A 「こーひー、もうちょっとい要りますか？」 B 「いいえ、どうも」

A: Do you want a little more coffee? B: No, I'm good.

Notes

"Mou chotto irimasuka" is a phrase used to ask if someone wants a little more of something, such as food, drink, or assistance. The word "mou" means "more" or "another," "chotto" means "a little" or "a bit," and "irimasuka" is the polite form of the verb "iru" (to need or want).

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

asking whether someone needs more offering more food or drink

showing consideration for the other person

Tags EN

immediate grammar polite expression question expression offer

eating and drinking situation considerate expression

That's right

とお
その通り

Sono toori

That's right

Variants

- その通り
that's right
- まさにその通り
exactly
- その通りです
that's exactly right

Adjusted Expression

A 「つまり、日本語では主語を省略することが多いということですね」 B
「はい、その理解で正しいです」

A: So, in Japanese, it is common to omit the subject. B: Yes, that understanding is correct.

Example

A 「つまり、日本語では主語を省略することが多いんですね？」 B 「その通り！」

A: So, in Japanese, it's common to omit the subject, isn't that right? B: That's right!

Notes

"Sono toori" is not just a simple agreement but an acknowledgment that the other person's logically derived inference is correct. It is a concise and clear way to affirm their reasoning. In this sense, it differs from a simple agreement like "Yes, that's right." The word "sono" means "that," and "toori" means "way" or "manner," implying correctness or accuracy.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

acknowledging someone's inference confirming that someone's understanding is correct

clear affirmation

Tags EN

immediate grammar colloquial response expression affirmation

confirming inference confirming understanding

I just remembered

いま おも だ
今、思い出した！

Ima omoidashita!

I just remembered!

Variants

- 今、思い出した！
I just remembered!
- 今思い出した！
Oh, I just remembered!
- そうだ、思い出した！
That's right, I remembered!

Adjusted Expression

いまおも だ あした かいぎ よてい
今思い出しました。明日、会議がある予定でした。

I have just remembered. I had a meeting scheduled for tomorrow.

Example

いまおも だ あした かいぎ
今思い出した！明日、会議があるんだった。

Oh, I just remembered! I have a meeting tomorrow!

Notes

"Ima omoidashita" means "I just remembered!" "Ima" means "now," and "omoidashita" is the past tense of "omoidasu" (to remember). Although it appears to be in the past tense, it expresses a realization happening at

this very moment. This usage is common when someone suddenly recalls something they had forgotten. Similarly, in "arun datta," even though the meeting is in the future, "datta" is used. This past form does not indicate a past event but rather the speaker's realization at the present moment.

Intent / Tags

Intent EN

expressing sudden recollection

realizing a forgotten plan

expressing renewed awareness

Tags EN

immediate grammar

colloquial

emotional expression

recollection

realization

present meaning of past tense

Colophon

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